

(a) MDS plot, individuals after excluding ethnic outliers

(b) Quantile-Quantile plot of SNPs in Swedish Endometrial cancer

Supplementary Figure 1. Each dot is an individual (case or control). The value of coordinate 1 (C1), C2, C3 and C4 represent the distance from the center of the graph in four dimensions representing genetic ethnicity based on the variants included in the analysis (a). The black dots represent observations scaled down by an inflation factor of 1.03. The diagonal red line represents the expected null hypothesis (= no association) (b).